

ACTIVATING NEWLY LEARNED VOCABULARY IN SPOKEN ENGLISH**Malikova Khurshida Sayfulla qizi**Webster University in Tashkent MA TESOL Program,
Master's degree student.<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20044746>

Abstract. *This article explores English language learners who are student, intermediate (B1) level in a local school. Most of the second language learners acquire new words through reading and explicit instruction but they gave struggled with using new words spontaneously in active way of spoken communication, they just learn them in passive ways. This gap between vocabulary knowledge and actual use often results in hesitant, limited speech despite adequate lexical recognition. In this article explain distinction between passive and active vocabulary and examines why newly learned words frequently fail to transfer learners' spoken production.*

Drawing on classroom-based teaching experience, the article presents practical strategies for helping leaners activate new vocabulary in speech, including repeated contextual exposure, the use of lexical chunks, guided speaking tasks, and low-risk communicative activities. A short classroom examples is provided to illustrate how teachers can support lexical retrieval and build learners' confidence in using new words orally. The article argues that systematic, supportive practice can effectively bridge gaps between learning vocabulary and using it in meaningful spoken interaction.

Keywords: *active vocabulary, passive vocabulary, lexical activation, second language acquisition, B1 learners, speaking fluency, vocabulary retention, communicative competence, text-based learning.*

INTRODUCTION

Students can speak easily and express their ideas in another language, they know this language new words and structure that are the main important part of the using of new language.

To be able to use new words, they should to activate their vocabularies in actively.

Vocabulary knowledge is frequency considered a foundation of language learning, yet many second language learners experience difficulty using newly learned words in spoken communication. In classroom contexts, students may recognise vocabulary items in reading or listening tasks but hesitate or fail to produce the same words when speaking. As a result, learners' oral output on a small set of familiar expressions. This challenge reflects a common gap between passive and activate vocabulary knowledge.

While learners may understand the meaning of new words, activating them during real-time speech requires rapid lexical retrieval, confidence, and sufficient contextual practice.

Without structured opportunities to use new vocabulary orally, words remain stored at a receptive level and do not become part of learners' productive language repertoire.

This article examines why newly learned vocabulary often fails to transfer into spoken use and explores practical classroom strategies that support vocabulary activation in speaking.

By focusing on guided practice, meaningful repletion, low-risk communicative tasks, the article aims to provide teachers with realistic approaches to help learners move from learning words to using them confidently in speech.

Activating new vocabulary through text-based speaking tasks

One practical way to help learners use newly learned vocabulary in speech is through carefully guided work with reading texts or short articles.

At intermediate level (B1), learners are capable of engaging with authentic or semi-authentic materials, such as graded CEFR texts, IELTS-style readings, or short opinion articles.

These texts provide not only new vocabulary but also ideas, grammatical structures, and discourse patterns that support spoken production. The process begins with selecting an appropriate text and asking learners to read general understanding.

During the reading stage, students are encouraged to highlight unfamiliar or advanced vocabulary items that appear relevant to the topic. Rather than translating these words into the first language, learners attempt to infer meaning from context and provide definitions in English.

This step promotes deeper lexical processing and helps learners develop paraphrasing skills, which are essential for speaking.

Once meanings are clarified, learners work with the new vocabulary actively. They are asked to produce at least two original, real-life sentences for each target word. This ensures that vocabulary moves beyond recognition and begins to enter productive use.

At this stage, attention is also drawn to grammatical structures that appear in the text. Learners are encouraged to incorporate both the new vocabulary and the observed grammatical patterns into their own sentences, reinforcing form-meaning connections.

Text-based work also supports idea generation, which is a common challenge in speaking tasks. For example, if the article discusses a topic such as vulnerability and its relationship to personal growth rather than weakness, learners gain conceptual content they can reuse in speaking activities.

This reduces cognitive load during speech, as students no longer need to generate ideas from scratch. Instead, they adapt and personalise ideas encountered in the text.

In the final stage, learners transfer vocabulary and ideas into speaking tasks, such as short discussions, individual responses, or extended turns similar to speaking exam formats. Because students have already encountered the language and content through reading and guided practice, they are more confident and fluent in oral production.

This integrated approach not only activates new vocabulary but also enhances overall language development by linking reading, grammar awareness, and speaking in a meaningful way.

CONCLUSION

Helping learners use newly learned vocabulary in spoken communication requires more than exposure to word lists or isolated practice. As shown in this article, vocabulary becomes activate when learners are given structured, meaningful opportunities to notice, process, and reuse new words in context.

Text-based speaking tasks provide a practical framework for achieving this by integrating reading, vocabulary development, grammatical awareness, and idea generation.

By guiding learners to define new words in English, produce original sentences, and apply both vocabulary and ideas in speaking activities, teachers can reduce hesitation and increase learners' confidence in oral production. This approach supports not only vocabulary activation but also overall communicative competence, as learners become more fluent, accurate, and willing to express their ideas.

Ultimately, activating vocabulary is a gradual process that benefits from consistency and purposeful classroom design. When vocabulary instruction is closely linked to speaking tasks, learners are more likely to move from knowing words to using them effectively in real communication.

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